

Book of Abstracts

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**Algae as a Sustainable Resource
for Food, Health and Industry**

Cultivation of *Arthrospira platensis* (*Spirulina*) Under Black Sea Conditions

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Abstract

EX-AQUA is a European-funded project designed to transform the National Institute for Marine Research and Development “Grigore Antipa” (NIMRD) into a centre of excellence in marine algae aquaculture. The project aims to strengthen scientific expertise and develop advanced technologies tailored to the specific environmental conditions of the Black Sea, fostering innovation and sustainable growth in the region’s blue economy. The EX-AQUA project aims to develop cost-effective technologies for producing *Arthrospira platensis* biomass adapted to the physicochemical conditions of the Romanian Black Sea sector. In this study, the *A. platensis* strain UTEX LB 2340 (or *Spirulina*) was cultivated under controlled laboratory conditions (20 ± 2 °C; $80\text{--}100$ $\mu\text{mol photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$; 16:8 h light:dark cycle) and progressively scaled up from small-volume flasks to 5 L photobioreactors and 10–25 L Algabag® systems. Four culture media were tested to assess adaptability and productivity: distilled water with F/2 (DW+F/2), filtered seawater (FSW), sterilised seawater with F/2 (SSW+F/2), and sterilised seawater with Zarrouk medium (SSW+Z). Growth was monitored by optical density (OD₆₈₀), while biomass production was quantified by dry weight. Significant differences were observed across media, with SSW+Z supporting the highest and most sustained biomass accumulation, followed by FSW as a low-cost operational alternative. In contrast, F/2-based formulations showed limited suitability at larger volumes. These findings demonstrate that *A. platensis* can be successfully cultured in closed photobioreactor systems using seawater-based media, provided that alkalinity and carbonate availability are optimized. This highlights the importance of medium composition and salinity control for maximizing biomass productivity in regional conditions. Overall, the findings confirm the feasibility of developing scalable *A. platensis* cultivation in Romania and provide a practical basis for future pilot- and industrial-scale applications in the Black Sea basin.

Modifying the Media Composition Can Be an Effective Approach to Achieve Maximum Pigments Production from *Spirulina platensis*

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Abstract

This study was conducted within the framework of the Egyptian-Romanian cooperation protocol between the National Research Center, Giza, Egypt and The Research and Development Institute for Aquatic Ecology, Fisheries and Aquaculture in Galati, Romanian

It's aimed to optimize the production of valuable pigments from the cyanobacterium *Spirulina platensis* by modifying media concentration.

Cultivation was performed in lab-scale systems, comparing standard and modified organic media where nitrogen, potassium, and phosphorus sources were strategically altered. Results demonstrated successful enhancement of biomass and pigment accumulation: dry biomass increased significantly from an initial 0.2 g/l to a maximum of 1.41 g/l after 13 days of cultivation. Over this growth period, total chlorophyll content rose from 0.35 mg/L to 1.59 mg/L, and total carotenoids increased from 1.17 mg/L to 2.7 mg/L. For phycocyanin (PC) recovery, cold maceration with phosphate buffer followed by 25% ammonium sulphate fractional precipitation yielded a concentration of 4.2 mg/g with a purity of 1.39 %. These findings confirm that modifying the growth media and optimizing the downstream extraction process are highly effective strategies for maximizing the production of high-value pigments from *Spirulina platensis*.

Nutraceutical and Functional Foods

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Abstract

The seminar focuses on the latest advancements and emerging trends in the development of food products designed to promote health and prevent disease. As consumer awareness of the relationship between diet and well-being continues to grow, there is increasing interest in nutraceuticals—bioactive compounds with therapeutic potential—and novel foods, including innovative ingredients and technologies that redefine the concept of nutrition. The seminar will explore scientific, technological, and regulatory aspects of these products, highlighting their role in addressing public health challenges, sustainability, and future food security. Participants will gain insights into current research, market perspectives, and the integration of novel food sources such as plant-based proteins, algae, fermented products, and functional ingredients. This event provides a multidisciplinary platform for researchers, industry professionals, and policymakers to share knowledge and discuss the future of food and health.

Highland microalgae and cyanobacteria: exploring the biotechnology potential of Andean freshwater ecosystems

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Abstract

The high-altitude lakes of the Ecuadorian Andes host microalgae and cyanobacteria adapted to intense UV radiation, low temperatures, and volcanic waters. These photosynthetic microorganisms exhibit exceptional metabolic and physiological resilience, making them promising for sustainable biotechnology. *Ettlia pseudoalveolaris* and *Pectinodesmus pectinatus* displayed contrasting adaptive strategies to high irradiance: *Ettlia* enhanced pigments and antioxidant defenses, while *Pectinodesmus* maintained constitutive photoprotection. *Ettlia* also showed antioxidant, antimicrobial, and antimutagenic activities, and acted as a biostimulant in *Chenopodium quinoa*, improving germination and salt-stress tolerance. *Coelastrrella tenuithec*a and *Parachorella kessleri* accumulated valuable pigments for natural dyes, and the cyanobacterium *Leptolyngbya* sp. produced exopolysaccharides with potential in soil recovery.

These findings highlight Andean highland microalgae and cyanobacteria as natural biorefineries, capable of producing bioactive molecules with applications in agriculture, nutrition, and environmental biotechnology, linking biodiversity to innovation and sustainability.

Effects of dietary Spirulina on the growth and health status of carp (*Cyprinus carpio*, Linnaeus 1758)

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Abstract

In previous studies, various beneficial effects have been demonstrated, particularly on growth performance, immunity, and disease resistance, through dietary supplementation with *Spirulina platensis* across multiple fish species. The main objective of this study was to investigate the impact of dietary supplementation with *S. platensis* on the growth performance of carp (*Cyprinus carpio*, Linnaeus, 1758) and on its health status, as assessed by key hematological indicators and blood biochemical parameters. Three experimental rearing variants were utilized to evaluate different concentrations of spirulina: V1 – control variant, without spirulina addition; V2 – experimental variant with 4% Spirulina powder added; V3 – experimental variant with 6% Spirulina powder added. Length-weight regression pointed out that the highest value, $R^2 = 0.948$, was recorded in the variant with 4% spirulina added, indicating a very strong correlation between spirulina addition and growth.

All performance indicators (biomass, individual growth, SGR, FCR, PER) recorded higher values in the variant where spirulina was added at a concentration of 4%, without affecting survival. The main conclusion resulting from the analysis of hematological indicators is that supplementation with 4% spirulina appears to promote erythropoiesis stimulation. This is reflected in increased hematocrit and erythrocyte count, indicators of increased activity of hematopoietic tissues. The evaluation of blood biochemical indices shows that the addition of 6% spirulina is the option with the best metabolic and immunological benefits, but it can induce intense physiological activity, as observed by the increase in AST. However, the reduced ALT values suggest that the liver tolerates this dose.

From the data obtained, we can conclude that spirulina is an effective and safe protein additive, and that 4% spirulina is the optimal dose for maximizing growth, protein utilization, and feed conversion, without adverse effects on fish health, being optimal in terms of cost/benefit ratio.

Valorization of *Posidonia oceanica* residues as sustainable growing media

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Abstract

The co-composting of *Posidonia oceanica* residues with other organic wastes, such as green wastes and dredged sediments, offers a sustainable solution for waste management in a circular economy perspective.

This study provides updated insights into the effectiveness of this process in generating high-quality components for growing media for agricultural applications. Key parameters such as pH, electrical conductivity, total organic carbon, humic carbon, enzymatic activities, bulk density, were considered for evaluate the suitability of the co-composts, in accordance with the national and international regulatory standards. In addition, the performance of the co-compost with *P. oceanica* and organic wastes as growing media component were investigated for the cultivation of agronomic plants. Special attention was given on the growing media changes as well as the plant health status during the plant cultivation to better assess the agronomic potential.

These findings support the use of *P. oceanica*- based composts as viable alternatives to peat and chemical fertilizers, contributing to resource recovery and environmental sustainability. The co-composting process not only valorises wastes but also provides a technically and ecologically sound strategy for producing high-quality growing media, reinforcing the transition toward circular bioeconomy models in agriculture.

EX-AQUA project - Macroalgae cultivation along Romania's Black Sea coast

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Abstract

EX-AQUA is a 3-year European funded project aimed at boosting scientific research in algae aquaculture, with a vision to make the National Institute for Marine Research and Development “Grigore Antipa” (NIMRD) of Romania a centre of excellence in algae farming, supporting innovation, climate action, and local economic development. This work introduces the project's primary objective and summarises the progress to date, aiming to promote sustainable algae aquaculture across the Black Sea region.

Our cultivations of the green algae, *Ulva spp.*, and the brown algae, *Cystoseira barbata*, have had considerable success in the first year of laboratory experiments. The aim is to create standardised methodologies for cultivating *Ulva spp.* for long-term economic benefits, and *C. barbata* for ecological restoration. Both species have shown promising growth under optimized conditions, with *Ulva spp.* now cultivated in 200-liter containers, an important achievement in the scaling-up process.

In parallel, *C. barbata* cultivation trials have been successfully conducted on various hard substrates and rope systems, with preparations underway for transplantation into the marine environment. This will set the basis of a standardised methodology for cultivating this species in laboratory settings for ecological reconstruction purposes.

Research on optimising methods for combating cyanobacteria in fish ponds

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Abstract

Cyanobacterial blooms are a major problem for aquatic ecosystems and fish farming activities, affecting water quality and the health of organisms. This paper compares the effectiveness of three control methods applied in experimental fish ponds: chemical treatment with copper sulphate, treatment with hydrogen peroxide, and an ecological method based on the use of barley straw. Over a period of eight weeks (June-August 2025), the physical and chemical indicators of the water, the concentration of chlorophyll-a and the density of cyanobacteria were analysed in four ponds with a history of algal blooms, namely cyanobacteria. The results show that hydrogen peroxide (5 mg/l) significantly reduced cyanobacterial biomass ($p < 0.05$) without major negative effects on other parameters, while copper sulphate had a rapid but temporary effect. Barley straw showed moderate effectiveness, with slow but favorable effects on maintaining ecological balance.

Algae from waste to sustainable vineyard resource

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Abstract

Sustainability is gaining an increasing importance in many industrial sectors and that includes the wine industry. Producers and operators in this sector recognize the importance of adopting sustainable practices not only whit the aim at environment preservation, but also for responsible resource management. In this context, adopting environmentally friendly strategies that reduce the use of pesticides and synthetic fertilizers in the wine sector becomes a priority. This concept has applications not only for sustainability and circular economy purposes but also addresses EU consumer food safety standards. The present study aims to review the main techniques that use algae to enhance soil properties and generally the health of the vineyard, respecting the principles of the circular economy.

Influence of nitrogen concentrations on biomass accumulation in *Spirulina (Arthrospira platensis)* cultivated in a photobioreactor

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Abstract

Spirulina, a blue-green, multicellular filamentous algae, has garnered increasing interest in the food and nutritional supplement industries due to its high protein and vitamin content. It provides substantial micronutrients and macronutrients, making it a promising candidate for aquatic feed. The large-scale production of spirulina depends on various factors, including nutrient availability, temperature, pH, and light levels. This study aimed to evaluate the effect of different nitrogen concentrations on the growth and biomass yield of *Arthrospira platensis* (spirulina) in a two-chamber photobioreactor (PBR) with each chamber containing 3 L. Cultures were grown for 12 days in standard Zarrouk medium, testing three nitrogen levels in the form of NaNO₃: limited (0.1 g/L), optimal (2.5 g/L), and enriched (5.0 g/L). The only variable altered was nitrogen concentration, while all other culture conditions—temperature at 30 ± 1 °C, continuous illumination, pH 9.0 ± 0.5, aeration with a constant CO₂ flow, and an initial inoculum density of 10%—were kept constant throughout the experiment. The dependent variables measured were biomass yield (g/L, dry weight) and specific growth rate (μ, d⁻¹). Preliminary results indicated that the optimal nitrogen concentration (2.5 g/L) supported the highest biomass growth and yield, whereas limited nitrogen significantly hampered development. Conversely, the enriched concentration resulted in a slight decrease in growth rate, possibly due to inhibitory effects. These findings suggest that an optimal balance of nitrogen availability is crucial for maximizing spirulina growth efficiency.